

Effects of Mastery Learning Approach on Performance in Geometry among Senior Secondary School Students in Northwest Zone, Nigeria

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to examine the effects of mastery learning approach on performance in geometry among senior secondary school students. Two research questions and two hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The study adopted Quasi-Experimental design. The population of the study comprised of senior secondary school one (SSI) students in the Northwestern states of Nigeria, and the distribution of the population was made up of male and female students from different backgrounds, cultures and location. Simple random technique through balloting was used in the selection of three states while purposive sampling techniques was employed in the selection of six schools; two from each state, three schools were selected from both state owned and private schools; two all-boys schools, two all-girls schools and two mixed schools. The sample size of 369 (201 males and 168 females) was used for the study. Geometry Performance Test (GPT) consisting of 20 standardized multiple choice test items adapted from West Africa Examination Council's past mathematics questions was used as the instrument for the study. Experimental groups were taught using mastering learning approach while the control groups taught with lecture method. The experiment lasted for four weeks. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used to present research questions while t-test for independent samples was used for testing of research hypotheses at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance. Results revealed that, the experimental group attained significantly higher achievement scores as compared to control group. On the issue of gender, the result shown that, mastery learning approach is gender friendly, since there is no significant difference between the performance of male and female subjects of the experimental group. It is recommended that, mastery learning approach should be adopted by mathematics teachers in teaching geometry and other perceived difficult topics in mathematics.

Keywords: Mastery Learning Approach, Students' Performance, Geometry

Introduction

The global trends in science teaching in recent time have been geared toward Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics education with greater emphasis being placed on industrial and technological development (Isma'il et al., 2019). In general, mathematics is connected with the development of any nation in the world, it opens and shuts doors for men and women than any other content area (Suleiman et al., 2020). Mathematical sciences play a foundational and cross cutting role in enabling

substantial advances across a broad array of fields. The knowledge of Mathematics is thus an essential tool in our society, and our daily life to overcome the difficulties we face. Its' importance is no doubt, associated with more academic and career opportunities. Today, mathematical methods pervade literary every field of human endeavor and play a fundamental role in economic development of any country. In our march towards scientific and technological advancement, we need nothing short of good performance in mathematics at all levels of education. Unfortunately, performance in

mathematics at the end of secondary education has not improved in the past decade (Udo & Udofia, 2014).

Geometry is the study of the size, shape and position of two and three dimensional shapes (Suleiman et al., 2020). Geometry is a link to many other topics in mathematics, specifically measurement, and is used daily by architects, engineers, and physicists and land surveyors (Umar, 2008). However in Geometry, one explores spatial sense and geometric reasoning. Geometry is found everywhere; in art, engineering, robotics, astronomy, space, sports and much more. Geometry is found in every stage of the secondary school curriculum and through to college and university. Geometric conceptions have been considered as a base for learning mathematics. The importance lies within the fact that Geometry is not only relating to Mathematical courses, but also concerning the development of students' cognitive skills, such as investigation, researching, criticizing, creative thinking, illustrating what they have learnt and self-expression (Erdogan & Lovgren, 2009). Furthermore, Geometry is necessary to our daily life and various professions because shapes and objects from Geometry are also available in our world.

Understanding Geometry is an important Mathematical skill since the world in which we live is "inherently geometric" (Clements & Battista, 2006). In the U.S for example, the National Council of Teachers of Mathematics working document, curriculum and evaluation standards for school mathematics [NCTM] (2010), states that Geometry "helps students (to) represent and make sense of their world". The Council further states that Geometry is an important school subject because it provides perspective for developing students' deduction reasoning abilities as the acquisition of spatial awareness (NCTM, 2010). Improving learners' Geometric thinking level is one of the major aims of Mathematics education since Geometric thinking is very important in many specific, technical and occupational areas (Hoffer, 2008).

Geometry achievement in secondary education, however, a whole body of research exists in which the low Mathematics performance of the Nigerian child is a common theme (Igwe, 2010). Going by the argument advanced by Igwe (2010) that performance in Mathematics as a whole is a good indication of performance in Geometry, specifically then students' knowledge of Geometry could be said to fall below expectation. Evidence could be drawn from WAEC Chief Examiner's report, which states that "candidates were observed to be generally weak in the area of Geometry" WAEC (2003). The WAEC

Chief Examiner's Report indicates that a "question on the angle properties of a triangle was also unpopular with the majority of the candidates. Many of the high school students in Nigeria could not comprehend" "the concepts and principles of angles in the same segment as well as alternate and corresponding angles".

A more interesting thing about Geometry is that student's performances and success have been shown not limited to the male or female alone. For instance, a study conducted by Umar, 2008, Zember and Blume (2009), Else-Quest et al., (2010), and Alex and Mammen (2014) reported that gender differentials among male and female students is converging, hence they perform similarly. Girls in girls' school perform excellently and boys in boys' school performed excellently too. When both boys and girls learn together, excellence reflects in them both. This is a clear reflection of gender friendliness. Again, Umar (2008) expressed that, motivation for Geometrical concepts is not limited to co-educational situation alone, single sex schools (boys or girls alone) enjoy same. Geometry is therefore gender friendly. However, Stoet and Geary (2013) opined that, gender differential in mathematical achievement is a global point of debate and has continued to be of interest and remain inconclusive.

The concept of Mastery-Learning was introduced in the American schools in the 1920's (Pankaj, 2019). Mastery learning involves a set of clear steps for selecting content, teaching and determining students' progress (Wong & Kang, 2012). The approach divides subject matter into units and each unit has a precise segment to complete with predetermined objectives. Students is expected to achieve mastery in the unit tests, before moving on to the following units. Students, who do not achieve mastery, receive remedial instruction and students who achieve mastery, have the opportunity to participate in enrichment activities (Pankaj, 2019). Hence, mastery learning approach gives room for individual students to learn at their own pace and capabilities.

Teachers who use mastery learning break down course material into manageable units and create formative tests for students on each unit, until a relatively high performance is attained by all the students in the formative test of a particular unit before the students can progress into the next unit of content (Adeniji et al., 2018). In Mastery Learning Approach each pupil attains mastery when he is able to give at least 80 percent correct response on a formative or summative test that has been constructed on the basis of instructional objectives with respect to that unit which each pupil is expected to achieve (Pankaj,

2019). The main goal of mastery learning approach is to have all students learn instructional material at roughly equivalent and high levels (Adeniji et al., 2018). Mastery Learning Approach is an instructional strategy that is designed to attain mastery of a learning task through variation of time and learning resources (Pankaj, 2019). Studies have been conducted to explore the effect of mastery learning approach on students' academic performance in mathematics and science (Adeniji et al., 2018) and different research findings have also reported the effectiveness of mastery learning approach in improving students' performances (Akinsola, 2007; Abakpa & Iji, 2013); Udo & Udofia, 2014; and Zakariyya et al., 2016 and Adeniji, et al., 2018).

However, some studies have shown that, majority of secondary students fear and dislike answering questions relating geometry both in internal and external examinations. For instance, Umar (2008) observed that out of 2,738 students that sat for pre-West Africa Examination Council (WAEC). (MOCK) examination in mathematics in Kebbi State only 562 (20.5%) attempted questions in geometry. The same pattern was reported by WAEC Chief Examiner's (2009 - 2015) annual reports. Beside fear and dislike of geometry, consistent poor performance in the topic had been reported (Ogunleye, 2010 & Ihejiro, 1995). Conversely, a survey study by Suleiman (2020) revealed that students' attitude towards geometry was relatively high generally, with male students having much higher positive attitude to geometry than their female counterparts. The main purpose of this study was to determine the effect of mastery learning approach on performance in in Geometry among Senior Secondary School Students in Northwest Zone of Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

1. To determine the effect of Mastery learning approach on academic performance in Geometry among the secondary school students in the Northwest Nigeria.
2. To examine gender-related effects of Mastery learning approach on academic performance in Geometry among the secondary school students in the Northwest Nigeria.

Research Questions

1. Is there any difference in the mean performance of students taught Geometry using mastery learning approach and those taught using the conventional lecture method?
2. Is there any difference in the mean performance of male and female students taught Geometry using mastery learning approach?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in the mean performance of students taught Geometry using mastery learning approach and those taught using conventional lecture method.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean performance of male and female students taught Geometry using mastery learning approach.

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study was a quasi-experimental and control group design employing Pretest and Posttest. The design involves two groups, the experimental group (EG) and control group (CG) to compare scores and means of two groups thereby making it possible to test the assumption of their equality. The experimental group were taught Geometry using mastery learning approach while the control group were taught using the conventional teaching method. Senior secondary school one (SSI) students with different capabilities formed the composition of all the groups.

The population of this study comprised of all the SSI students in the Northwest zone of Nigerian. The number of schools, types of school and population of students per school varies from state to state. Three (3) states, namely; Kaduna, Zamfara and Kano were randomly selected using balloting out of the nine (9) states in the northwest while purposive sampling technique was used to select two (2) schools from each. Through this sampling technique, three schools were selected from both state owned and private schools; two all-boys schools, two all-girls schools and two mixed schools (Table 1). Intact classes were used from each sampled schools, this is to ensure fair representation of different ability groups in each class. The selection of sample per class was guided by Central Limit Theory by Dana (2000), Fraenkel & Wallen (2000) and John & James (2011) which proposed that thirty or more subjects are considered as large sample for experimental research which by implication ensures better generalization of the findings. Therefore, the sample size of 369 was arrived at (201 males and 168 females). Geometry Performance Test (GPT) consisting of 20 standardized multiple choice test items adapted from WAEC past mathematics questions was used as the instrument for the study.

The two sets of lesson notes prepared by the researchers were used in teaching the content unit (geometry) selected for the study. The lessons last for four (4) weeks. The age of the students, class and duration of the period were considered in preparation of the lesson notes. The specific objectives and their

relation to content units were also considered in the preparation of the lesson notes. Two lesson plans were prepared each for experimental and control groups. Regular mathematics teachers of the schools selected for the study were trained as research assistant to assist in conducting the study, thereafter assigned to each group; mastery learning approach and conventional lecture method. The research assistants were closely monitored by the researchers during the teaching process to avoid deviation from the use of teachers' guide for each group throughout the treatment period.

Pretest was administered on the subjects, before the commencement of the experiment. At the end of the four week treatment period, all the students' in both experimental and control classes were exposed to GPT as post-test to determine the effectiveness of mastery learning approach. The GAT was also administered after the treatment. Both the pre-test and post-test were marked and recorded separately. The data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation scores and t-test at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

Is there any difference in the mean performance of students taught geometry using mastery learning approach and those taught using the conventional lecture method?

Table 1: Posttest mean performance for students in experimental and control groups

Group	N	Mean	Std.	Mean Difference
Experimental	197	16.75	3.22	5.54
Control	172	11.21	5.47	

Table 1 showed that the mean scores of experimental and control group are 16.75 and 11.21 and standard deviation of 3.22 and 5.47 respectively. The mean difference is 5.54, indicating that those

taught geometry using Mastery learning approach performed better than those taught using conventional lecture method.

Research Question 2

Is there any difference in the mean performance of male and female students taught geometry using mastery learning approach?

Table 2: Posttest mean performance for male and female students in experimental group

Gender	N	Mean	Std.	Mean Difference
Male	110	17.901	2.30	1.26
Female	87	16.64	2.85	

Table 2 showed that among those students taught geometry with mastery learning approach, males students performed a bit better as indicated by a mean of 17.90 (SD=2.30) than the female students

with a mean of 16.64 (SD=2.85). The mean difference of 1.26 shows that there is a difference in the performance of male and female students taught geometry using Mastery learning approach.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the performance of students taught geometry using mastery learning approach and those taught using the conventional lecture method.

Table 3: T-test analysis of the academic performance of students in experimental and control group

Variable	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-cal	t-crit	p-value	Decision
Experimental	197	16.75	3.22	367	14.08	1.97	.001	Significant
Control	172	11.21	5.47					

Table 4 showed that the p-value obtained was 0.001 which is < 0.05 , the value of t-calculated of 14.08 found is higher than the t-critical of 1.97 at 367 degrees of freedom. The null hypothesis was thus rejected. This means that there exists significant

difference in the performance of the experimental and the control group students.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the performance of male and female students taught geometry using mastery learning approach.

Table 4: T-test Analysis of the academic performance of male and female students in experimental group

Variable	N	Mean	SD	df	t-cal	t-crit	p-value	Decision
Male	110	17.90	2.30	195	0.21	1.96	0.084	Not Significant
Female	87	16.64	2.85					

Table 4 showed that, the p-value obtained was 0.084 which >0.05 . The value of t-calculated of 3.93 was found, is less than the t-critical of 1.96 at 195 degrees of freedom. Therefore, null hypothesis was retained. This means that, there is no significant difference between the performance of male and female subjects of the experimental group. Thus, the performance scores of male and female subjects taught geometry using mastery learning approach do not differed significantly.

Discussion of Findings

The result from statistical analyses related to the research question and hypothesis one as shown in Tables 1 and 2 respectively revealed that there exists significant difference in the performance of students taught geometry using mastery learning approach and those taught using conventional lecture method. This means that, the mastery learning approach significantly enhanced the performance of experimental group. This confirmed the findings of Pankaj (2019), Adeniji et al. (2018), Zakariyya et al. (2016) and Abakpa and Iji (2013) who reported that knowledge gains were found to be significant with experimental group using mastering learning approach more than their counterpart that were strictly taught using conventional lecture method in a classroom setting.

Result in Table 3 showed that among students taught geometry using mastery learning approach, male students performed a little bit better than their female counterparts. However, the statistical analysis of hypothesis two as shown in Table 4 revealed that the difference was not statistically significant. This indicates that mastery learning approach is gender friendly. The results supported the findings of Pankaj (2019), Adeniji et al. (2018) and Abakpa and Iji (2013) that male and female students achieved equally when taught geometry using mastery learning approach. Thus, mastery learning approach can help to improve or boost positive attitude of female students, whom Suleiman (2020) reported to have less positive attitude towards geometry than their male counterparts.

However, Udo and Udofia (2014) findings was not in agreement with this finding on gender.

Conclusion

Based on the findings from the study, the experimental group was found to attain significantly higher achievement scores as compared to control group. Thus, mastery learning approach is an effective strategy of enhancing academic performance of secondary school students in geometry. Also, the study showed that, mastery learning approach is gender friendly, because it increased the performance of both male and female students thereby bridging the academic gap between the two.

Recommendations

1. Mastery learning approach should be adopted as the method of choice in teaching geometry and other topics in mathematics that students find difficult to understand.
2. To successfully adopt mastery learning approach and its implementation in classroom, induction training of mathematics teachers through workshops and seminars is paramount.

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